

Novel Scalable Mesoporous Silica-Assisted Synthesis of High-Quality ϵ -Fe₂O₃
Nanoparticles Revealing Extraordinarily High Coercivity

Supporting Information

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Silica coated and mesoporous silica coated magnetite NPs were prepared by reactions whose compositions are summarized in Table S1.

Table S1: The composition of reaction for preparation of silica and mesoporous silica coated magnetite NPs and phase composition of prepared precursors after annealing at 250°C for 2 hours.

Silica coated magnetite NPs							
Sample	FeCl ₂ .4H ₂ O (g)	FeCl ₃ .6H ₂ O (g)	H ₂ O (mL)	CTAC (mL)	HN ₄ OH (mL)	TEOS (mL)	γ-Fe ₂ O ₃ :SiO ₂ (w/w)
M_SiO_1	1.87	4.02	34	0	7.2	3.0	1:0.47
M_SiO_2	1.87	4.02	31	0	7.2	6.0	1:0.93
M_SiO_3	1.87	4.02	28	0	7.2	9.0	1:1.36
M_SiO_4	1.87	4.02	25	0	7.2	12.0	1:1.84
M_SiO_5	1.87	4.02	22	0	7.2	15.0	1:2.32
M_SiO	18.7	40.2	340	0	72	66.0	1:1.13
Mesoporous silica coated magnetite NPs							
Fe ₃ O ₄ :SiO ₂	FeCl ₂ .4H ₂ O (g)	FeCl ₃ .6H ₂ O (g)	H ₂ O (mL)	CTAC (mL)	HN ₄ OH (mL)	TEOS (mL)	γ-Fe ₂ O ₃ :SiO ₂ (w/w)
M_mSiO_1	1.87	4.02	18	16	7.2	1.8	1:0.32
M_mSiO_2	1.87	4.02	18	16	7.2	3.6	1:0.57
M_mSiO_3	1.87	4.02	18	16	7.2	5.0	1:0.83
M_mSiO_4	1.87	4.02	18	16	7.2	5.4	1:0.88
M_mSiO_5	1.87	4.02	18	16	7.2	5.8	1:0.94
M_mSiO_6	1.87	4.02	18	16	7.2	6.2	1:1.00
M_mSiO_7	1.87	4.02	18	16	7.2	6.6	1:1.07
M_mSiO_8	1.87	4.02	18	16	7.2	7.2	1:1.17
M_mSiO_9	1.87	4.02	18	16	7.2	7.5	1:1.21
M_mSiO_10	1.87	4.02	18	16	7.2	8.0	1:1.26
M_mSiO_11	1.87	4.02	18	16	7.2	8.5	1:1.34
M_mSiO_12	1.87	4.02	18	16	7.2	9.0	1:1.56
M_mSiO_13	1.87	4.02	18	16	7.2	9.5	1:1.61
M_mSiO_14	1.87	4.02	18	16	7.2	10.8	1:1.80
M_mSiO	18.7	40.2	180	160	72	66.0	1:1.09

Figure S1: TEM images of silica-coated samples M_SiO_1 (a), M_SiO_3 (b), and M_SiO_5 (c), and mesoporous silica-coated samples M_mSiO_1 (d), M_mSiO_7 (e), and M_mSiO_14 (f) indicate increasing silica content correlated with increasing amounts of TEOS added during the preparation procedure.

The phase characterization of air-annealed mesoporous silica coated sample (M_mSiO) was performed by XRD analysis and the XRD patterns are depicted in figures S1(a-d). Identified crystalline phases were with following cell parameters: ϵ -Fe₂O₃ with orthorhombic structure (Pna21 space group) with cell parameter a = 0.5102 nm, b = 0.8781 nm and c = 0.9466 nm; maghemite (γ -Fe₂O₃) with a cubic structure (Fd-3m space group) with cell parameter 0.8345 nm; hematite (α -Fe₂O₃) with a hexagonal structure (R-3c space group) with cell parameters a, b = 0.5035 nm, c = 1.3748 nm.

Figure S2: XRD patterns of the resulting ϵ -Fe₂O₃ prepared by air-annealing of the scale-up sample at 1050 °C (a), 1075 °C (b), 1100 °C (c), and 1125 °C (d) for 1 (black line), 3 (red line), 5 (green line), and 10 (blue line) hours, respectively. All samples were measured without silica etching.

Figure S3: Hysteresis loops of M_mSiO annealed at 1100°C and 3 hours before (red line) and after 1M NaOH etching (black line).

Rietveld analysis description

The Rietveld analysis was conducted using High Score Plus software (version 4.8, now referenced in Section 2.2), with structural data for each phase derived from the PDF-5+ database. Phase profiles were modelled using the Pseudo-Voigt function, and the Caglioti function was applied to FWHM calculations to accurately describe peak broadening effects. The atomic coordinates and site occupancies were not refined for any identified phase. To demonstrate the quality of the fit, two representative diffraction patterns measured at room temperature and one measured at high-temperature (1100 °C)-accompanied by residual/difference plots and explanatory notes (Figure S4 and Figure S5). The fit quality metrics, R_{wp} and GoF (where R_{wp} is defined $R_{wp} = \left[\frac{\sum w_i(y_{io} - y_{ic})^2}{\sum w_i y_{io}^2} \right]^{1/2} \times 100$, and GoF, Goodness of Fit $\chi = \frac{\sum w_i(y_{io} - y_{ic})^{1/2}}{N-P}$), are provided with the respective figures. In other cases, the R_{wp} values ranged from 1.71 to 3.26, and the GoF values ranged from 2.1 to 4.2 for room temperature measurements. For high-temperature measurements, R_{wp} varied between 2.7 and 3.9, while GoF ranged from 1.8 to 2.5. These values indicate a satisfactory quality of the quantification fit, consistent with accepted standards in the field. These values indicate a suitable quality of the quantification fit consistent with accepted standards in the field. Regarding the discussion on magnetite presence, magnetite does not occur in any annealed samples. After annealing at a minimum temperature of 250 °C, only maghemite is present in the annealed specimens, as confirmed by lattice parameter values which align well with those reported for maghemite in the literature.

Figure S4: Demonstrative examples of fitted diffraction patterns with residuals for two representative samples: M_SiO (a) and M_mSiO (b), measured at room temperature.

Figure S5: Demonstrative example of a fitted diffraction pattern with residuals for the M_SiO sample heated to 1100 °C after one hour of annealing.